

Effect of pre-treatment on the germination of *Abrus precatorius* Linn. by soaking in water

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Abstract

In the present investigation, seeds of *Abrus precatorius* were subjected to pre-treatment by soaking in water to achieve early germination by breaking dormancy.

It was found that, on 7th day 20% germination was achieved in the case of seeds kept as control, whereas it was 60%, 60%, 90%, 50%, 50% and 30% respectively in the seeds soaked in water for 2, 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 hours. Thus the best exposure time for seeds to be soaked in water was 6 hours. However at extended soaking periods the germination percentage was poor.

Key words : *Abrus precatorius*, germination, soaking, dormancy.

The seeds of most of the plants germinate when they are provided with favourable environmental conditions such as air, moisture and suitable temperature etc. However, there are many more plants whose seeds do not germinate even that provided with favourable environmental conditions. Germination of such seeds may be delayed for days, weeks, months or even years due to some chemical inhibitors, impermeability, ripening after the harvest, thick seed coat and immature development of embryo.

In the present study, seeds of *Abrus precatorius* were tested for their germination potential and shortening of dormancy period. Initial studies showed that there is very meagre percentage of germination in the seeds of this

plant. Therefore, it was thought imperative to undertake this investigation to find out the factor that can break the dormancy of *Abrus precatorius* seeds and increase its germination percentage. The seeds were subjected separately to x-ray exposure, acid saccharification, sand saccharification, mechanical injury and pre-treatment by soaking in water. The best among these was found to be pre-treatment by soaking in water.

Various factors affect the process of germination which are briefly dealt herewith:

1. *Temperature:*

It affects cellular metabolic and growth

rates. Seeds from different species even seeds from the same plant germinate over a wide range of temperatures. Seeds often have a temperature range within which they will germinate, and they will not do so above or below this range. Many seeds germinate at temperatures slightly above room temperature *i.e.*, 16-24°C, while others germinate only in response to alternations in temperature between warm and cool. Some seeds germinate when the soil is cool *i.e.*, 0-5°C (*Pyrus malus*), and some seeds germinate when the soil is warm *i.e.*, 24-32°C (maize).

2. Oxygen:

It is required by the germinating seeds for metabolism. It is used in aerobic respiration, the main source of the seedlings energy until it grows leaves. If a seed is buried too deeply within the soil or the soil is waterlogged, the seed can be oxygen starved. Some seeds have impermeable seed coats that prevent oxygen from entering the seed, causing a type of physical dormancy which is broken when the seed coat is worn away enough to allow gas exchange and water uptake from the environment.

3. Light :

Most seeds are not affected by light or darkness but many seeds, including species found in forest settings, will not germinate until an opening in the canopy allows sufficient light for growth of the seedling. In nature, some seeds require particular conditions to germinate, such as the heat of a fire (*e.g.*, many Australian nature plants), or soaking in a water body for a long period of time.

4. Water:

Mature seeds are often extremely dry

and need to take in significant amounts of water, relative to the dry weight of the seed, before cellular metabolism and growth can resume. Most seeds need enough water to moisten them but not enough to soak them and most seeds show higher germination percentage by soaking them in water before sowing such as *Abrus precatorius*. The uptake of water by seeds is called imbibition, which leads to the swelling and the breaking of the seed coat.

Seed dormancy can originate in different parts of the seed, for example; within the embryo, in other cases, the seed coat is involved. Dormancy breaking often involves changes in membranes, initiated by dormancy-breaking signals. This generally occurs only within hydrated seeds. Dormancy of seeds is due to one or a combination of several different factors². It may be impermeability of seed coats to oxygen, dormant embryos, mechanically resistant seed coats or combination of these factors. Some seeds such as those of *Brassica alba* show secondary dormancy in which seeds are capable to germinate when they are harvested, lose this capacity after being kept in an environment for a while which is not favourable. The induced dormant period is called as secondary dormancy. This induction of secondary dormancy is used to preserve the seeds for future use.

There are a number of techniques available for breaking the dormancy of seeds. These include; impaction, scarification, stratification, alternating temperatures and pressure.

Studies on germination and dormancy of seeds have been carried out by various workers on different types of species. These include; the studies of Raven *et al*,¹¹ on biology of

plants. Effects of reduced oxygen tension on germination and seedling growth was found by Siegel and Rosen,¹⁴ Pfahler,¹⁰ investigated *in vitro* germination characteristics of maize pollen to detect biological activity of environmental pollutants. Self-incompatibility in plants was shown by Takayama and Isogai¹⁵. Barton¹ worked on hastening the germination of some coniferous seeds. Crocker² studied the mechanics of dormancy in seeds. Effects of the visible spectrum upon the germination of seeds and fruits was also shown by Crocker³. Life-span of seeds was investigated by Crocker⁴. Denny and Stanton⁶ suggested chemical treatments for shortening the rest period of pot grown woody plants. The development of secondary dormancy in embryos of *Ambrosia trifida* was shown by Davis⁵. Morinaga⁹ studied the germination of seeds under water. In vitro measurement of pollen tube growth inhibition was investigated by Martin⁸.

The healthy seeds of *Abrus precatorius* were collected from Raisen (M.P). The seeds were surface sterilized with 0.1% HgCl₂ solution for

5 minutes to kill or remove the surface adhering microbes. Uniform sized seeds were then transferred to sterilized PetriPlates provided with filter paper pads.

Six replicates of soaked and control were kept for germination studies. The filter paper pads were moistened as and when needed. The emergence of radicle was taken as germination. The soaking duration was for 2, 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 hours.

Germination started from 2nd day onwards and the germination percentage was recorded from 3rd day. The germination percentage was 0%, 60%, 60%, 90%, 50%, 40% and 30% respectively under control, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 hours soaking treatment. On the 5th day, it was 20%, 60%, 60%, 90%, 50%, 50% and 30% under the same treatments and finally on 7th day, the germination percentage was recorded to be 20% (control), 60% (2 hours), 60% (4 hours), 90% (6 hours), 50% (8 hours), 50% (10 hours) and 30% (12 hours) soaking treatment. The results are shown in the following table-1.

Table-1 Showing the effect of pre-treatment on the germination of *Abrus precatorius* by soaking in water.

Duration of soaking	% germination on 3 rd day	% germination on 5 th day	% germination on 7 th day
Control	0 %	20 %	20 %
2 hours	60 %	60 %	60 %
4 hours	60 %	60 %	60 %
6 hours	90 %	90 %	90 %
8 hours	50 %	50 %	50 %
10 hours	40 %	50 %	50 %
12 hours	30 %	30 %	30 %

A perusal of table-1 indicates the pre-treatment of *A. precatorius* seeds by soaking in water improves the germination percentage compared to the seeds which are untreated and kept as control. As is evident, the best exposure time of the seeds of this plant to soaking in water was found to be 6 hours in which 90% germination was achieved on 7th day after sowing, whereas, it was 60% under 2 hours, 60% under 4 hours, 50% under 8 hours, 50% under 10 hours and 30% under 12 hours exposure to soaking in water. And all two hours to twelve hours exposure to soaking in water proved to be germination enhancer compared to the control which could stimulate only 20% seeds to germinate. The dormancy in *A. precatorius* seeds may be due to seed coat which is not permeable to water and oxygen in first few days and there may be presence of germination inhibitors in the seed coat which are removed by varying exposure to soaking in water. Higher duration of seed exposure to soaking (12 hours) resulted in poor germination percentage compared to the rest of the treatments, may be due to damage of embryo by excess water and therefore lower germination percentage was found. Higher duration of soating probably produced water logged condition, leading to poor germination.

In the present investigation, the ideal time of water soaking was found to be 6 hours which supported the higher germination percentage of the treated seeds. Hence, it is inferred that *A. precatorius* seeds, before sowing should be pre-treated by soaking in water for 6 hours so as to achieve higher germination percentage.

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